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MODERN APPROACHES TO THE DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF FEBRILE SEIZURES IN CHILDREN

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Abstract. *Febrile seizures are brief seizure episodes that occur in young children in the context of fever and are not associated with central nervous system infections or disorders. This condition affects approximately 2–5% of children between the ages of 6 months and 5 years and is one of the leading causes of seizures in pediatric practice.*

The aim of this review is to provide practical recommendations for emergency care physicians who manage such patients in clinical settings.

Methods

To prepare this review article, an analysis of 48 recent scientific publications on the diagnosis, treatment, and prognosis of febrile seizures in children was conducted. The review included sources published in international databases such as PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, and eLibrary between 2020 and 2025.

Results

Simple febrile seizures account for approximately 70% of all cases, complex febrile seizures — 25%, and febrile status epilepticus — 5%. The latter is one of the most common causes of status epilepticus in young children. It has been established that the main provoking factors are viral infections (influenza, human herpesvirus type 6, adenovirus), as well as certain bacterial infections, particularly otitis media.

Keywords: *febrile seizures, children, diagnosis, treatment.*

СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ К ДИАГНОСТИКЕ И ЛЕЧЕНИЮ ФЕБРИЛЬНЫХ СУДОРОГ У ДЕТЕЙ

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Резюме. Фебрильные судороги представляют собой кратковременные судорожные эпизоды, возникающие у детей раннего возраста на фоне лихорадки и не связанные с заболеваниями центральной нервной системы. Это состояние наблюдается у приблизительно 2–5 % детей в возрасте от 6 месяцев до 5 лет и занимает ведущую позицию среди причин судорог в педиатрической практике.

Целью данной обзорной публикации является предоставить практические рекомендации врачам неотложной помощи, сталкивающимся с такими пациентами в клинической практике.

Методы: Для подготовки данной обзорной статьи был проведён анализ 48 актуальных научных публикаций, касающихся диагностики, лечения и прогноза фебрильных судорог у детей. В обзор были включены источники, опубликованные в международных базах данных PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science и eLibrary за период с 2020 по 2025 год.

Результаты: Простые фебрильные судороги составляют около 70 % всех случаев, сложные — 25 %, а фебрильный эпилептический статус — 5 %. Последний является одной из наиболее частых причин эпилептического статуса у детей раннего возраста. Установлено, что основными провоцирующими факторами являются вирусные инфекции (грипп, герпесвирус 6 типа, аденовирус), а также бактериальные патологии, в частности, средний отит.

Ключевые слова: фебрильные судороги, дети, диагностика, лечение.

БАЛАЛАРДАҒЫ ФЕБРИЛЬДІ ҰСТАМАЛАРДЫ ДИАГНОСТИКАЛАУ ЖӘНЕ ЕМДЕУДІҢ ЗАМАНАУИ ТӘСІЛДЕРІ

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Түйіндеме. Фебрильді құрысу — бұл орталық жүйке жүйесінің ауруларымен байланысты емес, дене қызуының жоғарылауына жауап ретінде ерте жастағы балаларда пайда болатын қысқа мерзімді құрысу эпизодтары. Бұл жағдай 6 айдан 5 жасқа дейінгі балалардың шамамен 2–5 %-ында кездеседі және педиатриялық практикада құрысу ұстамаларының ең жиі кездесетін себебі болып табылады. Осы шолу мақаласының мақсаты — клиникалық практикада мұндай пациенттермен жиі кездесетін жедел жәрдем дәрігерлеріне практикалық ұсыныстар беру.

Әдістер: Бұл шолу мақаласын дайындау барысында фебрильді құрысуы бар балалардың диагностикасы, емі және болжамы мәселелеріне арналған 48 өзекті ғылыми жарияланымға талдау жүргізілді. Шолуға 2020 жылдан 2025 жылға дейінгі аралықта PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science және eLibrary халықаралық дерекқорларында жарияланған дереккөздер енгізілді.

Нәтижелер: Фебрильді құрысу жағдайларының шамамен 70 %-ын қарапайым фебрильді құрысулар, 25 %-ын күрделі құрысулар, ал 5 %-ын фебрильді эпилептикалық

статус құрайды. Соңғысы ерте жастағы балалардағы эпилептикалық статустың ең жиі кездесетін себептерінің бірі болып табылады. Негізгі қоздырушы факторлар ретінде вирустық инфекциялар (тұмау, 6-шы типтегі герпес вирусы, аденовирус), сондай-ақ бактериялық аурулар, соның ішінде отит медиасы анықталған.

Түйін сөздер: фебрильді құрысу, балалар, диагностика, емдеу.

Febrile seizures are the most commonly observed type of seizures in children under the age of 5 [1]. They are defined as episodes of seizure activity occurring in the presence of fever (body temperature of at least 38 °C or 100.4 °F) in children aged 6 to 60 months, without signs of central nervous system infection [2]. Although the condition is benign in most cases, febrile seizures are often perceived by parents as life-threatening events and are a common reason for visits to pediatric emergency departments [3].

The aim of this review article is to provide practical recommendations for emergency care physicians who encounter such patients in clinical practice.

Methods.

To prepare this review article, an analysis of 48 up-to-date scientific publications on the diagnosis, treatment, and prognosis of febrile seizures in children was conducted. The review included sources published in international databases such as PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, and eLibrary between 2020 and 2025. This article reviews the existing classifications of febrile seizures and highlights issues related to their diagnosis, treatment, and prognosis. The incidence of febrile seizures ranges from 2% to 5% among children in the United States and Western Europe [4]. According to several studies, this figure may reach 8–10% in Asian populations [5]. The highest incidence is observed during the second year of life, with approximately **90%** of first febrile seizures occurring before the age of three.

Discussion

Febrile seizures occur more frequently during the winter months, which correlates with an increased incidence of febrile illnesses during this period. Some studies indicate a higher prevalence among boys, while others do not find statistically significant gender differences. Genetic predisposition is believed to play a substantial role in the development of febrile seizures: approximately one-third to one-half of affected children have a family history of seizures.

The most common infectious triggers of febrile seizures are viral illnesses such as influenza, adenovirus, parainfluenza, and human herpesvirus type 6 (which causes roseola in infants)[7]. Among bacterial causes, otitis media is considered the most frequent condition associated with the onset of febrile seizures.

Febrile seizures can also occur in response to vaccination, particularly following administration of vaccines containing a measles component (such as the measles, mumps, and rubella vaccine), as well as combination vaccines for diphtheria, tetanus, and pertussis, the 13-valent pneumococcal conjugate vaccine (PCV13), and the influenza vaccine [8].

Previously, it was believed that the rapid rise in body temperature was the primary trigger for seizures. However, current evidence suggests that the peak fever level is the most critical factor. In simple terms, the higher the temperature, the greater the risk of febrile seizures. One study found that the likelihood of febrile seizures nearly doubles with each degree Fahrenheit above 101 °F [9].

Clinical manifestations of febrile seizures include loss of consciousness, irregular or labored breathing, pallor or cyanosis of the skin, foaming at the mouth, eye rolling or fixed gaze, as well as generalized or focal jerking and convulsive movements of the limbs. Facial muscles are often involved. Additionally, atonic and tonic seizures may also occur. Following a seizure episode, a postictal period is often observed, which may present as drowsiness, anxiety, or altered consciousness lasting up to 30 minutes. In some cases, postictal paralysis, known as Todd's paralysis, may develop [10]. Febrile seizures are classified as simple, complex, and febrile status epilepticus based on their duration, presence of focal neurological signs, and recurrence within the same febrile episode. Approximately 70% of all febrile seizures are classified as **simple**, about 25% as complex, and around

5% are diagnosed as febrile status epilepticus. Febrile status epilepticus is the most common form of status epilepticus in children [11]. The evaluation of a child with febrile seizures should begin with a thorough history and physical examination to identify the underlying cause of fever. When taking the history, it is important to assess the characteristics of the seizure itself (including its duration), recent illnesses, use of antibiotics, presence of seizures or epilepsy in the personal or family history, recent vaccinations, and immunization status for *Haemophilus influenzae* type B and *Streptococcus pneumoniae*.

The physical examination should focus on detecting signs of meningitis, such as decreased level of consciousness, increased irritability, bulging fontanelle, nuchal rigidity, and decreased muscle tone.

However, in younger children, the clinical manifestations of meningitis may be subtle or entirely absent. As with any patient experiencing a seizure, children with febrile seizures should have their serum glucose levels assessed. Routine laboratory testing is generally not required in cases of simple febrile seizures, as electrolyte abnormalities are extremely rare in these instances.

Additional laboratory investigations should be performed individually, based on the child's clinical history and physical examination findings.

The causes of fever in children with febrile seizures are similar to those in febrile children without seizures. Moreover, children with simple febrile seizures do not have an increased risk of developing serious infections such as pneumonia, urinary tract infections, bacteremia, or bacterial meningitis, compared to other febrile children [12]. The American Academy of Pediatrics (AAP) does not recommend routine neuroimaging for children with simple febrile seizures. The primary clinical objective in evaluating a child with febrile seizures is to rule out bacterial meningitis, since approximately one in four children with meningitis presents with seizures. If a child with febrile seizures exhibits signs and symptoms suggestive of meningitis, lumbar puncture is mandatory [13].

Children with febrile status epilepticus have a significantly higher risk of developing bacterial meningitis compared to those with simple or complex febrile seizures. Studies have reported meningitis rates ranging from 12% to 17% in such cases [14]. In most instances, febrile seizures resolve spontaneously before the child arrives at the emergency department. However, if the seizure persists, international guidelines agree that antiseizure therapy should be initiated for any tonic-clonic activity lasting longer than 5 minutes. The approach to managing febrile status epilepticus is identical to the treatment of status epilepticus of other etiologies [15].

Results

Simple febrile seizures account for approximately 70% of all cases, complex febrile seizures — 25%, and febrile status epilepticus — around 5%. The latter is one of the most common causes of status epilepticus in young children. It has been established that the main provoking factors are viral infections (such as influenza, human herpesvirus type 6, and adenovirus), as well as bacterial conditions, in particular, otitis media. Febrile status epilepticus typically does not resolve spontaneously and often requires the administration of more than one antiepileptic drug. If the seizure persists, repeated doses of benzodiazepines may be administered at 5-minute intervals. If there is no response, second-line anticonvulsants such as levetiracetam, fosphenytoin, sodium valproate, or phenobarbital may be necessary [16]. Since fever is the main trigger for febrile seizures, it might seem logical to assume that antipyretic medications could help prevent recurrence. However, results from multiple studies evaluating the effectiveness of antipyretics for the prevention of febrile seizures have not supported this hypothesis. The American Academy of Pediatrics (AAP) has concluded that although antipyretics may improve a child's overall comfort, they do not prevent the occurrence of febrile seizures.

One of the main concerns among parents is the possibility of long-term neurological consequences following febrile seizures. However, population-based studies have not demonstrated a convincing association between simple or complex febrile seizures, as well as febrile status epilepticus, and subsequent development of cognitive or neurological impairments [17]. Recurrence of febrile seizures is a well-studied phenomenon. Approximately one-third of children who have

experienced at least one episode will have a recurrent seizure later in childhood. The most significant risk factor for recurrence is the child's age at the time of the first episode. According to one study, the recurrence rate is around 50% in children whose first seizure occurred before the age of one, while in children over the age of three, the risk decreases to 20% [18].

Conclusion.

Febrile seizures are the most common type of seizure in preschool-aged children and often cause significant parental anxiety, as they are frequently perceived as potentially life-threatening events.

The introduction of vaccines against *Haemophilus influenzae* type B and *Streptococcus pneumoniae* has significantly influenced the diagnostic approach to children with febrile seizures, allowing for a reduction in the extent of diagnostic procedures.

The classification of febrile seizures based on their duration and other clinical features plays a crucial role in determining the treatment strategy and predicting the course of the condition.

Conflict of Interest. The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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